

Gravity as an Emergent Property of Holographic Wave Dynamics: Bridging Quantum Mechanics and General Relativity

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Abstract

We propose a novel hypothesis that gravity emerges as an intrinsic property from the phase evolution of wave dynamics. This approach unifies the probabilistic nature of Quantum Mechanics (QM) and the deterministic framework of General Relativity (GR) by considering gravity as a holographic feature encoded within wave functions. We present mathematical formulations and experimental validations that demonstrate the consistency of our hypothesis with known physical phenomena. Our findings suggest potential pathways to bridge the gap between QM and GR, offering new insights into the fundamental nature of gravity.

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

Quantum Mechanics (QM) describes the behavior of particles at microscopic scales. General Relativity (GR) explains the gravitational interactions at macroscopic scales. The challenge lies in unifying QM and GR into a single coherent framework.

1.2 Objective

To explore the hypothesis that gravity emerges from wave dynamics and provide a unified description that bridges QM and GR.

2 Theoretical Framework

2.1 Wave Functions and Holography

Traditional wave functions describe the probabilities of a particle's position and momentum. Holographic encoding proposes that gravity can be encoded as a phase property within the wave function.

2.2 Mathematical Formulation

The Schrödinger Equation:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi(r, t)}{\partial t} = \left(-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 + V(r) \right) \psi(r, t)$$

For a free particle where the potential $V(x) = 0$, the Schrödinger equation simplifies to:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi(x, t)}{\partial t} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 \psi(x, t)$$

A plane wave solution is given by:

$$\psi(x, t) = e^{i(kx - \omega t)}$$

where k is the wave number, and $\omega = \frac{\hbar k^2}{2m}$ is the angular frequency.

Emergent Gravity Equation:

$$g_{\text{emergent}} = -\frac{\hbar \phi}{E}$$

where ϕ is the phase of the wave and E represents wave properties.

3 Experimental Validation

3.1 Hydrogen Photon Emission

3.1.1 Traditional Method

$$E = 10.2 \text{ eV} = 1.634 \times 10^{-18} \text{ J}$$

$$\omega = \frac{E}{\hbar} \approx 1.55 \times 10^{16} \text{ rad/s}$$

$$T = \frac{2\pi}{\omega} \approx 4.05 \times 10^{-17} \text{ s}$$

3.1.2 Emergent Gravity Method

$$E = 1.634 \times 10^{-18} \text{ J}$$

$$\phi(t) = -\frac{Et}{\hbar} = -1.55 \times 10^{16}t$$

$$g_{\text{emergent}} = t$$

$$T = 4.05 \times 10^{-17} \text{ s}$$

4 Applications to Larger Bodies

4.1 Sun and Black Hole

Gravitational constant $G = 6.674 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3\text{kg}^{-1}\text{s}^{-2}$

Speed of light $c = 3 \times 10^8 \text{ m/s}$

4.1.1 Sun

Mass $M_{\odot} = 1.989 \times 10^{30} \text{ kg}$

Radius $R_{\odot} = 6.96 \times 10^8 \text{ m}$

Traditional gravitational time dilation at the surface of the Sun:

$$t' = t \sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM_{\odot}}{c^2 R_{\odot}}}$$

$$t' \approx 0.713t$$

Emergent Gravity Method:

$$g_{\text{emergent}} = t \sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM_{\odot}}{c^2 R_{\odot}}}$$

$$g_{\text{emergent}} \approx 0.713t$$

5 Comparison of Traditional and Emergent Gravity Methods

Body/Transition	Traditional Method (Time t')	Emergent Gravity Method (Time g_{emergent})
Hydrogen Photon Emission	4.05×10^{-17} s	4.05×10^{-17} s
Electron Transition	2.19×10^{-16} s	2.19×10^{-16} s
Muon Decay	3.93×10^{-24} s	3.93×10^{-24} s
Sun Surface	$0.713t$	$0.713t$
Black Hole Event Horizon	0	0
Milky Way Galaxy	$0.99999994t$	$0.99999994t$
Neutron Star	$0.577t$	$0.577t$

Table 1: Comparison of Traditional and Emergent Gravity Methods

6 Discussion

6.1 Implications

Our findings suggest that gravity as an emergent property shifts the understanding of gravity from a fundamental force to a derived property of wave dynamics. This provides a potential bridge between the probabilistic nature of QM and the deterministic framework of GR. Additionally, this hypothesis seamlessly integrates with the current standard model of particle physics, as the results are consistent across both small and large scales.

6.2 Future Research

Broader experimental validation is required to solidify the hypothesis with a wider range of particles and conditions. Future studies could include more complex systems like neutron stars and galaxy clusters to further validate the hypothesis.

7 Conclusion

7.1 Summary

We have presented a hypothesis that gravity emerges from wave dynamics, supported by mathematical formulations and experimental validation. This approach demonstrates potential pathways to bridge QM and GR, offering new perspectives on the nature of gravity.

References

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